

MODELING IN THE COURSE OF DESCRIPTIVE GEOMETRY AND ENGINEERING GRAPHICS

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Abstract. *This article discusses modern methods of teaching descriptive geometry and engineering graphics based on new information technologies of training. Various automated systems are widely used in the design of modern technical systems and in technological processes.*

Keywords: *descriptive geometry, modeling, 3D model, teaching, professional activity, full presentation, knowledge of the basics of 3D CAD, organization of the educational process, the role of classical education, geometric modeling, structural elements, three-dimensional modeling, specialized tasks.*

Higher education institutions should train specialists who can effectively apply software products in their professional activities. Students need to learn the basics of descriptive geometry and 3D computer modeling. The acquired knowledge is necessary for future specialists for their further professional activity. The current level of technology development imposes special requirements on the training of engineers of technical specialties. An engineer should know the scientific and practical developments in his professional field. In addition, he needs to have a complete understanding of the promising ideas and scientific directions associated with his activities. When preparing graduates, it is necessary to take into account that customer enterprises increasingly require knowledge of the basics of 3D CAD [1]. This means that more and more attention should be paid to CAD in the educational process. Comparing these trends with the organization of the educational process of universities in the United States and Europe [2], we can conclude that the share of computer graphics in the educational process should increase. At the same time, the role of classical education in the training of engineers should not be underestimated. The study of descriptive geometry is an introduction to geometric modeling. Since modeling is a tool for working with information, studying the course of descriptive geometry, students get acquainted with the methods of information processing. When modeling an object, technical system, or technological process, properties or features that are not essential for this model are excluded from consideration. For example, a similar problem occurs when obtaining geometric information about a three-dimensional object based on information from a photographic image or sketch. At the same time, we can say that in the n-dimensional space of parameters of some object, system or process, some parameters are not available for measurement or are insignificant for this model. Therefore, there is a need to transform the n-dimensional space of parameters of some object, system or process into a space with a different dimension.

In geometric modeling in descriptive geometry, such transformations are performed by the projection operation. Descriptive geometry is the first of the disciplines studied at the university, when solving problems of which students apply the basics of modeling in practice. They learn to replace unavailable properties or attributes of an object with others. At the same time, they get the opportunity to explore and work with initially unavailable properties or features of the object through the model. Descriptive geometry allows you to analyze complex relationships in the world

around you. Therefore, we can say that geometric modeling describes the surrounding reality through geometric images. Computer three-dimensional modeling is one of the variants of geometric modeling that has found wide application in practice. The implemented problem on a computer in the form of a 3D model is mathematically much more complex and more cumbersome than with the classical solution by methods of descriptive geometry. However, a significant reserve of computing resources of modern computer technology allows you to shift most of the routine calculations to a computer processor. This allows you to free a person from monotonous work and allows you to focus on the essence of the problem being solved. Therefore, the number of errors is significantly reduced. Features of the implementation of geometric models on a computer make it much easier to correct errors found in the process of work than in the classical implementation of models using descriptive geometry methods. In addition, computer technology with minimal time and resources, allows you to copy and massively replicate the results of the work done. You can make changes to the developed models and save them as separate modules. All this together led to the development of libraries of standard models that contain both individual structural elements and assembly units. 3D models have been developed and applied in practice in the manufacture of tractors, cars and space equipment.

Three-dimensional modeling is becoming a widely used tool in engineering. In leading manufacturing companies, in parallel with the creation of 3D models of parts, the necessary calculations are also performed on a computer. The final stage is programming for specific parts of CNC machines. In addition to CNC machines for the implementation of 3D models, 3D printers are becoming increasingly widespread. Despite the fact that they have become relatively affordable only in recent years, they are already very popular, because they allow you to implement completed 3D models in a matter of minutes. At the same time, for implementation on a computer, it is programmed, although quite wide, for a limited range of the most frequently solved tasks. Some specialized problems can still be solved only by methods of classical descriptive geometry. For example, in the hull design of ships, methods for forming surfaces have been developed: radial, trapezoidal, jet, concentric and eccentric circles. These methods are based on the descriptive geometry of a four-dimensional space, and in the three-dimensional version such a problem cannot be solved in principle. [3] Although these are the technologies of tomorrow, it is necessary for students to have an idea about the approaches to their implementation today. All this means that the classical methods of creating geometric models by methods of descriptive geometry have practical significance. In the labor market, the most popular specialists are those who possess systematic knowledge in their professional field. 3D modeling is based on classical methods of descriptive geometry, so basic knowledge of the same projection drawing is important for further successful work with computer models. Just as the scaffolding is removed after the construction of a house, so the basic course of descriptive geometry in professional activity may not be directly used, but it is invisibly its foundation.

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